

SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF REINFORCEMENT IN PM Al-4Cu/SiC_p MMCs: COMPUTER SIMULATION AND CHARACTERISATION BY EDX ANALYSIS

I.C. Stone and P. Tsakirooulos

Department of Materials Science and Engineering,
University of Surrey, Guildford, Surrey GU2 5XH, U.K.

ABSTRACT

The large scale use of discontinuously reinforced Al alloy MMCs has been hindered, in part, by the lack of attaining reliably uniform distributions of the particulate reinforcement. This paper will examine a method which measures the variation in local chemical composition by EDX analysis for characterising the spatial distribution of SiC_p in PM Al MMCs produced by hot isostatic pressing, forging and rolling, and by Conform.

A computer simulation of the technique based on local EDX analysis will be presented and it will be shown that it is possible to discern between random dispersions of particles of different volume fractions, between microstructures which exhibit clusters of different sizes, and between microstructures which exhibit clusters of different aspect ratio. Limitations in the use of the technique will also be discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The lack of a homogeneous dispersion of the reinforcement in particulate reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) has been identified as a contributory factor to the inadequate reliability and commercial success of these materials. The spatial distribution of the reinforcement not only affects the mechanical properties of the MMCs but also the ability to process [1] and heat treat [2] them. Despite this no technique currently exists which is either practical or sensitive enough to accurately describe the spatial distribution of particulate reinforcements in MMCs.

Previous attempts at the characterisation of microstructures have been reviewed [3], but the most promising of these, techniques based on the distribution of interparticle spacings and the Dirichlet tessellation, have been found to be insufficiently sensitive [4].

Lange and Hirlinger [5] have described a technique, using local chemical analysis, for the characterisation of Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ compacted mixtures. This technique has also been applied to Cu/W mixtures [6]. The first stage in the experimental procedure is to take a number of

energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectra, at different positions in the sample at each of a series of magnifications (scan areas). The standard deviation of the proportion of X-rays attributable to a minor component element is plotted as a percentage of the mean against the magnification or more accurately the scan area. When the analysis is performed over a very small scan area (high magnification) which is smaller than the scale of segregation then the variation in X-ray concentration will be large. As the scan area increases (magnification decreases) the variation in X-ray concentration falls until a plateau is reached at which point the area scanned is significantly larger than the scale of segregation. If the scale of segregation increases then the plateau in the curve is reached at larger scan areas, and hence the curve is translated. Whilst these workers have studied the effect of bulk volume fraction, and the quality of mixtures to some extent, they did not consider the complication of comparing mixtures which contain second phase particles of different sizes.

This paper develops the technique proposed by Lange and Hirlinger, for the characterisation of the microstructures of SiC particulate (SiC_p) reinforced Al MMCs produced by different powder metallurgy (PM) routes.

SIMULATION

A computer program was written for the purpose of illustrating the principle of the EDX technique for characterising microstructural homogeneity of particulate second phase systems. The simulation begins by producing either a random distribution of dots (single pixels) (Fig.1a), or arrays of square or rectangular clusters with randomly placed dots within them (Fig.1b-e). The overall density of dots, the size of cluster and the cluster aspect ratio can all be chosen.

Figure 1. Computer generated arrays of dots. (a) random, (b) 10x10 clusters, (c) 20x20 clusters, (d) 10x20 clusters, (e) 10x30 clusters.

A square measuring box is then randomly superimposed on the generated array, and the number of dots which fall within this box is calculated. This procedure is repeated the required number of times, the mean and standard deviation of the number of dots counted are calculated, and hence the coefficient of variation (ratio of standard deviation to mean) is derived. The measuring box size is then altered and the process repeated. The coefficient of variation of number of dots counted is then plotted against the side length of the measuring box. Results of the simulation will now be discussed for a number of random distributions of varying density of dots, and for a number of arrays of square and rectangular clusters of constant dot density.

Fig.2 shows the results of the simulation for random dispersions of 2.5%, 5%, 10% dot densities. The curves are all of a similar shape. At small measuring box sizes there is a large variation in the number of dots counted in each measurement. The coefficient of variation then falls off quickly towards zero at larger measuring box sizes. The rate at which the curves fall towards the plateau is dependent upon the overall dot density of the computer generated dispersion, i.e. as the dot density decreases the plateau is reached at larger box sizes and hence the curve is translated to the right.

Figure 2. Results of the computer simulation for random dispersions of different dot densities.

The simulated results for different size square clusters for an overall dot density of 5%, along with those for the random dispersion of the same dot density are shown in Fig.3a. The curves for the square clusters are of a similar shape to that of the random dispersion, but are no longer smooth. They exhibit a damped cyclic type of shape, such that the minima are reached at a period of twice the side length of the measuring box. This cyclic behaviour is a function of the geometry of the chosen generated structure and would be eradicated if a checker board type of geometry were used for the array of clusters. Despite this geometric effect of the chosen cluster arrays there is the underlying dependence of the coefficient of variation of dot counts on the size of the measuring box as seen in the random case. As the simulated microstructure moves from a random dispersion of dots to small clusters and then to larger clusters, that is to say the microstructure becomes less homogeneous, then the curves translate to the right and a larger box size is necessary to distinguish the scale of segregation.

Figure 3. Results of the computer simulation for arrays of (a) square clusters of different sizes, and (b) rectangular clusters of different aspect ratios.

A similar damped cyclic effect is also seen when considering the aspect ratio of clusters in an array of the type used here (Fig.3b). Again the period of the cycle is a function of the length of the cluster. As the aspect ratio of the cluster increases the inhomogeneity of the dispersion of dots increases and the curves once more translate to the right.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS

MMCs were produced by mixing batches of gas atomised Al-4wt%Cu alloy matrix powder of varying mass median diameters with either 3 μ m, 17 μ m or 29 μ m SiC_p. The exact combinations used are given in Table 1. Blended mixtures of matrix powder with 20wt% SiC_p were cold compacted into aluminium cans and vacuum degassed for 4h to 6h at 648K. These were then sealed, hot isostatically pressed (HIPped), and scalped to leave fully dense MMC billets of 45mm diameter. The HIPped billets were then hot forged through their diameters in two stages to a thickness of 22mm. This was followed by hot rolling to a thickness of 2mm in fifteen passes. Full details of the production of this series of MMCs are given in [3]. Samples of these materials were taken for characterisation after the HIPping and hot rolling stages.

A further series of MMCs were produced by continuously extruding blended mixtures of pure Al matrix powder and SiC_p to bars of 8mm diameter. Details of the combinations of matrix and SiC_p particle diameters used are also given in Table 1.

Table 1. Combinations of matrix and SiC powder sizes used for MMC production

Production Route	Matrix Mass Median Diameter (μ m)	SiC _p Particle Size (μ m)	Matrix:SiC _p Particle Size Ratio
HIP / Forge & Roll	35	29	1.21
	40	17	2.35
	80	29	2.76
	50	17	2.94
	40	3	13.33
	50	3	16.67
Conform	32	75	0.43
	15	13	1.15
	32	25	1.28
	60	25	2.4
	32	13	2.46
	60	13	4.62

PROCEDURE

Specimens for EDX analysis were prepared using standard metallographic techniques and carbon sputter coated to prevent charging of the SiC_p reinforcement prior to mounting in the microprobe.

EDX analysis was done on a Jeol 8600X Superprobe, with a programmable stage, using an accelerating voltage of 20kV. The area analysed was kept at a constant proportion of the CRT display, such that the actual area of analysis could be controlled by altering the magnification of the microscope. The net number of X-rays were calculated for the central twelve channels of the Al(K_{α}) and Si(K_{α}) peaks. The proportion of Si X-rays to the sum of the Al and Si X-rays was evaluated at each position, and the mean and standard deviation calculated at each magnification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The microstructures of the HIPped MMCs all showed necklacing (Fig.A1) of the prior matrix particles by the reinforcement. The severity of this necklacing was dependent upon the ratio of the matrix to reinforcement particle diameters. The MMCs with large matrix:reinforcement particle size ratios exhibited severe necklacing whilst as the particle size ratio tended towards unity the necklacing became less perceptible. More photomicrographs can be found in [3,7]. Results of the EDX analysis technique for the HIPped MMCs are shown in Fig.4. It is not correct to compare measurements taken at the same scan area for materials which contain different sizes of reinforcement since for a constant volume fraction the spacing between particles increases linearly with the size of the particles [8]. It is therefore necessary to normalise the scan area by the square of the reinforcement particle diameter. It can be seen from Fig.4 that as the matrix:reinforcement particle size ratio increases, i.e. the level of microstructural inhomogeneity increases, the curves are translated to the right as predicted by the simulation. It is important to note that it is possible to discern between small differences in the spatial distribution of the reinforcement, shown by the translation in the curves where there are only small differences in the matrix:reinforcement particle size ratio.

Figure 4. EDX analysis results for the HIPped MMCs.

The microstructures of the forged and rolled MMCs are caused by the deformation of the as HIPped structure. Detailed photomicrographs can be found in [3,7]. As the matrix:reinforcement particle size ratio increases, the HIPped microstructure becomes more necklaced and the rolled microstructure becomes more highly segregated (e.g. Fig.A2). Results of the EDX analysis (Fig.5) also show that the microstructure becomes less homogeneous with increasing particle size ratio.

Figure 5. EDX results for longitudinal sections of the rolled MMCs.

The microstructures of the Conformed MMCs were more complex [9]. Some microstructures showed reasonably well dispersed reinforcement, some exhibited levels of inhomogeneity which were different in central regions of the bar cross-sections to the outside (Fig.A3), and some showed pockets containing highly segregated fines of reinforcement (Fig.A4). These microstructures proved to be too complicated for the local EDX technique to discern between them, as shown in Fig.6, and hence further development of the technique is required.

Figure 6. EDX results for the Conformed MMCs.

Although the EDX technique can be very sensitive to small variations in the level of microstructural inhomogeneity there are a number of limitations to its universal use as a method for such characterisation. These are the lateral spreading of the electron beam increasing the scan area by an unknown amount, the possibility of the X-ray peaks overlapping, and the lack of distinct segregation of chemical elements between the two phases.

CONCLUSIONS

A technique which uses local EDX analysis for characterising the spatial distribution of particulate reinforcement in Al based MMCs has been discussed. Computer simulations have shown that it should be possible to discern between random dispersions of particles of different volume fractions, between microstructures exhibiting clusters of different sizes, and between microstructures exhibiting clusters of different aspect ratios. The EDX based technique has been used to characterise the spatial distribution of SiC_p reinforcement in PM Al based MMCs produced by HIPping, by forging and rolling, and by Conform. To compare microstructures which contain differently sized reinforcing particles the area of analysis must be normalised by the square of the diameter of the particles. The technique has been found to be very sensitive to small variations in microstructural homogeneity, however its universal use for any two phase system is limited by the chemical composition of the two phases and the positions of the X-ray energy peaks on the EDX spectrum. Further development of the technique is required so that microstructures where the reinforcement is segregated by size can be characterised.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank Professor J.E. Castle for the provision of laboratory facilities, BOC for the supply of atomising gases, and Miss C.E. Wilson for the collection of part of the EDX data. One of us (ICS) would also like to thank the Ministry of Defence Procurement Executive, Farnborough, for a CASE award. Support of the University of Surrey research programme on gas atomisation by the SERC is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

1. I. C. Stone and P. Tsakirooulos, The effect of the spatial distribution of reinforcement on the fabrication and heat treatment of (Al-4wt%Cu)-SiC particle metal matrix composites. *Mater. Sci. Eng. A189*, 285-290 (1987).
2. I. C. Stone, C. E. Wilson and P. Tsakirooulos, Matrix ageing in hot isostatically pressed SiC particulate reinforced Al-4wt%Cu alloys, in preparation.
3. I. C. Stone, PhD thesis, University of Surrey (1994).
4. I. C. Stone and P. Tsakirooulos, The characterisation of the spatial distribution of reinforcement in Al/SiC_p MMCs, Part 1: techniques based on microstructure, accepted for publication in *Mater. Sci. Techn.* (1995), in press.
5. F. F. Lange and M. M. Hirlinger, Phase distribution studies using energy dispersive X-ray spectral analysis. *J. Mater. Sci. Let.* **4**, 1437-1441 (1985).
6. B. Altan, Z. Misirli and H. Yorucu, The determination of homogeneity in multiphase mixtures. *Z. Metallkunde*, **81**, 221-228 (1990).
7. I. C. Stone and P. Tsakirooulos, The spatial distribution of reinforcement in PM Al/SiC_p MMCs and its effect on their processing and properties, *Proc. 9th Int. Conf. Composite Materials, Vol.1 Metal Matrix Composites*, Ed. A. Miravete, University of Zaragoza, 271-278 (1993).

8. C. W. Corti, P. Cotterill and G. A. Fitzpatrick, The evaluation of the interparticle spacing in dispersion alloys. *Int. Met. Rev.* **19**, 77-88 (1974).
9. I. C. Stone, C. E. Wilson and P. Tsakirooulos, Microstructural characterisation of Conformed SiC particulate reinforced aluminium MMCs, in preparation.

APPENDIX

Figure A1. Highly necklaced structure of a HIPped MMC.

Figure A2. Highly segregated structure of a rolled MMC.

Figure A3. A Conformed MMC showing a different spatial distribution of the reinforcement in the centre of the bar than the outer region.

Figure A4. A Conformed MMC showing pockets of SiC fines.